

Empirical Force Field Calculations and Conformational Analysis of Benzene Molecule

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Force field calculations using convergent energy minimizations were carried out for the conformational analysis of benzene molecule. The calculated parameters for the structure is in agreement with the experimental data. The calculated vibration frequencies follow the Mair and Hornig assignments of frequencies of benzene.

THE concept of theoretical conformational analysis of organic molecules was proposed more than three decades ago and benzene, being the simplest compound in the aromatic series, has attracted attention¹⁻⁹. In the present work, it is aimed to develop force field for aromatic molecules, and the conformational analysis of benzene has been done through energy minimization in which all internal degrees of freedom are allowed to relax.

Calculations :

The computational methods and programmes used were developed from the consistent force field system of Lifson and Warshel¹⁰ as modified by Niketić and Rasmussen¹¹. No internal coordinate has been kept fixed, which may be considered to be an advantage over the reported approaches¹⁻⁹. The minima on the potential energy surface is then related to equilibrium conformations.

To construct the model of the structure of matter, the concept of Born-Oppenheimer separation is used and all electronic motions are dropped. It is assumed that all interactions are additive and mutually independent. The potential energy of the system is formulated as :

$$V = E_b + E_\theta + E_\phi + E_{nb}$$

where bond deformation : $E_b = \sum_{\text{bonds}} \frac{1}{2} K_b (b - b_0)^2$

valence angle deformation : $E_\theta = \sum_{\text{angles}} \frac{1}{2} K_\theta (\theta - \theta_0)^2$

torsional deformation : $E_\phi = \sum_{\text{torsions}} \frac{1}{2} K_\phi (1 + \cos 3\phi)$

non-bonded interactions :

$$E_{nb} = \sum_{i>j} \epsilon_{ij} \left\{ \left(\frac{r_{ij}^*}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - 2 \left(\frac{r_{ij}^*}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right\}$$

The quantities b , θ , ϕ and r_{ij} are variables which characterize a given conformation. All other quantities are adjustable parameters depending upon the

particular force field chosen for the study. The initial values of the parameters K_b , b_0 , K_θ , \dots , r_{ij}^* , are collected from literature¹² or are guessed.

The potential energy of the atomic arrangement is calculated starting from a set of values of the energy parameters¹², a description of the topology of the arrangement and a set of atomic coordinates. The minima of the energy are obtained at those points in configurational space which correspond to equilibrium conformation for the chosen set of energy functions. The curvatures in these points are the force constants of vibrational motion around the equilibria. On expanding the energy in a Taylor series around one of the minima we have

$$V(r) = V(r_0) + \sum_i \left(\frac{\delta V}{\delta r_i} \right)_0 \delta r_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i>j} \left(\frac{\delta^2 V}{\delta r_i \delta r_j} \right)_0 \delta r_i \delta r_j + R$$

The first term is the equilibrium energy. The relative energies of different equilibrium conformations of the same molecule are significant in determining which of the conformations is to be preferentially selected.

The second term vanishes at equilibrium as a necessary condition for equilibrium where the gradient vanishes.

The third term represents the energy of vibration and here the force constants are derived from each individual interaction between two coordinates.

Initial conformations : Both planar and distorted conformations are taken at the initial stage to obtain the equilibrium conformation of benzene.

Energy minimization : All initial conformations produced have a high energy gradient and are thus far from minimum. The gradient was lowered¹¹ first by a Davidon-Fletcher-Powell algorithm (10-20 iterations) and then by a modified Newton algorithm (10-15 iterations) which uses second partial derivatives in the search for a minimum. Minimization was achieved when the norm of the gradient becomes less than 10^{-6} kJ mol⁻¹ Å⁻¹.

IBM computer 370/165 was employed for the calculations.

TABLE 1—FORCE FIELD^a PARAMETERS FOR BENZENE MOLECULE

K_b	b_0	K_θ	K_ϕ	ϵ_{ij}	r^*_{ij}
900 (C—C)	1.40 (C—O)	142 (C—C—C)	16 (C—C—C—C)	0.072 (C—)	3.901 (C—)
712 (C—H)	1.08 (C—H)	89 (C—C—H)		0.040 (H—)	3.150 (C—)

^a Energies are expressed in kJ mol^{-1} ; lengths in \AA ; angles in rad.; the force constants are expressed correspondingly.

TABLE 2—GEOMETRY OF BENZENE MOLECULE

Distance	Calculated (Present work)	Experimental		
		Gas	Liquid	Solid
C—C (\AA)	1.4022	1.393 \pm 0.005 ^a 1.397 ^b 1.397 ₄ \pm 0.001 ^c 1.400 ^d	1.41 \pm 0.01 ^e	1.392 ^f 1.411 \pm 0.013 ^g 1.392 \pm 0.007 ^h
C—H (\AA)	1.0848	1.08 \pm 0.02 ^a 1.081 ^b 1.084 \pm 0.005 ^c 1.0897 ^d 1.095 \pm 0.008 ^h
Angles C—O—C ($^\circ$)	120	120 ^a		

^a Electron diffraction (ref. 13)

^b Electron diffraction (ref. 14)

^c Rotational Raman spectrum (ref. 15)

^d Electron diffraction (ref. 16)

^e X-ray diffraction (ref. 17 and 18)

^f X-ray diffraction (ref. 19 and 20)

^g Proton diffraction (ref. 21)

^h Neutron diffraction (ref. 22)

Results and Discussion

As initial conformations, planar and a number of distorted or non-planar conformations were taken. On minimization, only one minimum was obtained corresponding to a planar conformation which is the equilibrium conformation. The final values of the parameters are reported in Table 1.

Non-bonded interactions :

In the calculations the interactions between 1 and 3 atoms have been excluded and the non-bonded interactions for 1, 4 and higher interactions were taken into account. For E_{nb} , both Lennard-Jones 12-6 as well as 9-6 potentials were tried and the former was found to be appropriate in the minimization.

Geometry of benzene molecule :

Comparison of the bond lengths and valence angles at the minimum energy level with the experimental values are reported in Table 2. It may be seen that the calculated values agree with the observed values.

Vibration frequencies :

Ingold *et al*^{23,24} assigned the vibration frequencies of benzene and its various deuteroderivatives and discussed the assignment of the frequency corresponding to the C—C stretching vibration of symmetry type B_{2u} . In benzene and hexa-deuterobenzene molecule, they assigned the vibration frequencies as 1618 and 1600 cm^{-1} , respectively. However, Mair and Hornig²⁵ by an analysis of the infrared spectra of crystalline benzene found that the vibration frequencies correspond to 1309 and 1282 cm^{-1} .

A group of workers²⁰⁻²² supported the assignment of Ingold *et al* while Duinker and Mills² and Tatevskii *et al*³ used the vibration frequencies reported by Mair and Hornig. The frequencies obtained in the present work agree with those of Mair and Hornig²⁵ assignments. Though optimization of the force field has not been done, it generally agrees with the experimental values.

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